

INTEGRATIVE TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPING SOCIO-CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

Mahmudova Sumbula Abdumalikovna

Researcher of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11366619>

Abstract: In this article, theoretical-methodological foundations of social-creative competence development in future pedagogues, cognitive-methodical system of social-creative competence development and development of social activity skills and creative competence in future pedagogues in the conditions of reforms are studied. Also, the integrative methodology of development of socio-creative competence was analyzed on the example of Pedagogical sciences.

Key words: pedagogic, social-creative, competence, cognitive-methodical, social activity, skill, qualification, competence, integrative approach, development, pedagogical model, reproductive, functional.

INTRODUCTION. In the course of teaching "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" on the basis of an integrative approach, the development of social-creative competence in future pedagogues, in turn, the practicalization of this process, that is, the organization of lectures, seminars and practical training requires the implementation of a technological approach.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of social activity among future pedagogues in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, Kh. Tojiboyeva, G. J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasovlar studied the development of social competence, while N. Azizkho'jayeva, A. Aripdzhanova, G. Ibragimova studied the aspects of teaching students to work creatively and developing different competencies in them. In the research works of N. Muslimov, O'. Tolipov, F. Exsonova, the problems of creative education were studied by M. Kadirova, Sh. Pozilova, A. Khalikov, Sh. Sharipov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Based on the general description of the technological approach, the following technology for developing socio-creative competencies of future pedagogues was developed in the course of teaching "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" based on an integrative approach within the framework of the research, which is called "Integrative socio-creative competence technology" was named.

The fact that integrability is the primary feature of this technology is expressed in its name. As any system consists of an internal structure, element (elements), the elements of this technology, which is described as a system, are

its stages, and it consists of three stages that require and complement each other.

The first stage of the technology is called "Acquiring knowledge about social creativity" and is carried out on the basis of solving the following tasks:

1. Introducing the knowledge of "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" and defining the next tasks for the pedagogue in this process.

2. Learning materials within the scope of "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" are introduced and the student begins to develop social and creative skills. At this stage, interactive methods and problem situations are used. In this process, it is important to achieve individual activities of students within the scope of possibility. The process of individual work ensures that each student approaches his task independently. As a result, one's personal opinion, personal attitude and creative qualities grow.

The second stage of the technology was called "Directing the subjects to the development of socio-creativity", and at this stage, the tasks of identifying and analyzing the importance of creativity in social-educational and socialization were solved in the study of subjects. The social and creative skills formed in the student at the previous stage are developed at the level of competence. Determination and analysis of the importance of creativity in socio-educational and personal socialization in the study of subjects was organized on the basis of individuality-oriented games.

The third stage of the technology was called "Transformation of topics into a system for the development of socio-creative competence", at this stage, special attention was paid to the development of socio-creative competence in solving problem situations and solving the tasks of using socio-creative solutions in the performance of training tasks, i.e. acquired knowledge, developed skills, skills, and other practical and intellectual capabilities become systematic, gradually develop and reach the status of competence.

Analysis of problematic situations is a highly effective method for developing social and creative competence in students, through which they acquire knowledge about analyzing tasks that arise in their daily and future professional activities, and finding the right solution.

The use of problem situations in the development of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues helps to solve the following tasks:

- 1) Creative solution of problem situations of future pedagogues within the framework of the knowledge acquired in learning on the basis of "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" subjects;

2) to establish thinking of future pedagogues based on socio-creativity in solving problem situations;

3) efficient use of time, concentration of attention and mental power of future pedagogues in solving the situation;

4) development of individual and group intellectual activity. Develop the ability to find several correct options for solving a problem.

Completion of problem tasks is carried out on the basis of socio-creative competence solutions of future pedagogues, which allows them not only to think about the topic, but also to learn additional information.

In the course of our research, a 3rd-stage technology for the development of socio-creative competence was developed for the 2nd and 4th year students of the "Pedagogy" discipline within the framework of "Social pedagogy" and "Creative pedagogy" disciplines.

Below we present the technology of social-creative competence development implemented in the teaching of "Social pedagogy" for 2nd year students:

Topic: Content, purpose and tasks of the science "Social pedagogy". (Levels 1-2 of the technology are intended for lecture training, and level 3 is for practical training)

Stage 1. 1.1. The lecture was organized by the teacher as a "press-conference". The students were asked to ask questions about the topic in writing, and the teacher organized the questions according to their content and explained the lecture. During the lecture, all the students' questions were answered. Students were also given the opportunity to ask oral questions. Along with answering the questions, the teacher paid attention to the logical discussion of the studied issue.

1.2. Students were introduced to the material of the lecture on the subject of "Content of Social Pedagogy" and guided to the initial perception of social-creative skills.

Stage 2. The identification and analysis of the socio-educational and personal importance of socialization and creativity in the study of the topic "Content of social pedagogy" was carried out on the basis of the following individuality-oriented games:

2.1. "Judge" game. Students were divided into pairs. Students were assigned the task of asking their partners questions about the topic. The first student addressed the second and the second student addressed the first with two questions each. In the process of creating questions, students tried to focus their

attention within the new topic and create them in a way that gave importance to the content of the questions. This game challenged them to be quick and think broadly.

2.2. Game "Futurologist". The game is aimed at developing personal motivations of students, discovering new qualities and self-development.

First, it was suggested to imagine, create a future image with clear goals, desires and aspects, and move from scattered visions to an image with a clear vision. He was given the opportunity to be fully satisfied with the vision of the quality he wanted to achieve, and to have a positive feeling. It was suggested to compare the future image with the past and present situation, to think about what is superfluous or what can be done to achieve the set goal.

Stage 3. 3.1. A problematic situation. The young specialist started working at the school. When he studied the team of pedagogues at the school, it became clear that there is no unity in this team. That is, they split into two groups consisting of supporters of the school director and the deputy director of educational affairs.

What do you think a young professional should choose in such a situation?

3.2 Students completed the following assessment tasks based on their social and creative competence solutions.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the possession of socio-creative competence is considered the basis that ensures the effective organization, development and prospective movement of future pedagogues. Development of an improved model of the teaching system focused on the development methodology of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues based on the requirements of the time, determination of the educational style and development strategy of professors and teachers suitable for students, classification of various pedagogical tools and methods, it follows that it enables the use of available resources and other auxiliary materials.

References:

1. Avazboev A.I. Improvement of training of teachers of labor and vocational education based on the integration of the content of educational subjects. Name. diss. 13.00.02. Ph.D. Tashkent, 2001.-В.
2. Аксютин, З. А. Концепция компетентностной подготовки к социальному воспитанию в вузе / З. А. Аксютин // Сибирский педагогический журнал № 3. -Новосибирск, 2011.-С. 130.
3. Алимов С.Ш. Формирование социокультурной компетенции учителей общеобразовательных школ республики Таджикистан. Дисс. ...канд. пед. наук. Душанбе, 2009.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

4. Баркунова О.В. Формирование профессиональной компетентности социального педагога в процессе педагогической практики: Автореф. ... дисс. канд. пед наук. Шуя, 2010.
5. Варлакова Ю.Р. Развитие креативности будущих бакалавров педагогического образования в вузе: автореф. дисс. канд. пед. наук: – Красноярск, 2013. – 17 с.
6. Гончаров С.В. Социальная компетентность личности: сущность, структура, критерии и значение// Образование и наука. 2004. № 2 (26). С. 3 – 18
7. Khodjaev B.Kh. Cultivation of natural thinking among students of general education school in modernized didactic support vocitacid: ped. science doctopi ...dicc. -Т.: 2016. - В.76-77.

